

Chemical Constituents of *Lyonia formosa*

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Investigations on the leaves of *L. formosa* (N.O. Ericaceae) were undertaken because of its hypotensive activity, found during the screening programme at C.D.R.I., Lucknow and to isolate and identify the toxic principles that cause death due to respiratory failure of mules, goats and cattle.

Alcoholic (50%) extract of the air dried leaves (collected in NEFA) after removal of solvent was extracted first with benzene and then with *n*-butanol. Column chromatography of the above benzene extract (on alumina) furnished four crystalline substances, A, B, C and D. A, m.p. 55°, C₂₆H₅₄* was identified as hexacosane by mixed m.p. determination.

Substance B, m.p. 155–60° after benzylation and chromatography over alumina afforded two compounds melting at 188–90° [α]_D+90°[†] and at 258–60° [α]_D+50°. On hydrolysis they yielded the triterpenes m.p. 179–80° [α]_D+85°, C₃₀H₅₀O and m.p. 208–10° [α]_D+20°, C₃₀H₅₀O, identical with α -amyrin and lupeol respectively (mixed m.p. and superposable I.R. Spectra).

Substance C, m.p. 135–36° [α]_D–34° gave positive L.B. test and was identified as β -sitosterol through mixed m.p. determination and preparation of its acetate m.p. 132° [α]_D–40°, C₃₁H₅₂O₂.

Substance D, m.p. 252–57° [α]_D+68.7 (EtOH) gave a positive Noller test for triterpenoid and negative TNM test. The I.R. spectrum of this substance indicated the presence of hydroxy, carbonyl and gem dimethyl functions and the U.V. spectrum had no maxima above 215 m μ . D, could not be identified due to its paucity.

The butanol extract after removal of the solvent and usual purification gave a single spot on ascending and circular paper chromatograms (*n*-BuOH-AcOH-H₂O; 4 : 1 : 5). The glycoside on hydrolysis with 5% H₂SO₄ (18 hrs), gave aglycone which was found to be a mixture of two compounds on TLC. The sugars liberated during this hydrolysis were identified by paper chromatography as glucose, rhamnose and arabinose. The aglycone, when chromatographed over silica gel using methanol-benzene (5 : 95) gave two yellow crystalline compounds I and II. Compound I, m.p. 315–20°, C₁₅H₁₀O₇ was found to be quercetin by mixed m.p. determination and preparation of its pentaacetate m.p. 197–98° while compound II, m.p. 165–67° (Found : C, 66.50; H, 6.30), λ _{max} 226 and 286 (EtOH), 242 and 296 (NaOH/EtOH), 223 and 287.5 (AlCl₃/EtOH) and 228 and 287 m μ (NaOAc/EtOH) could not be identified due to low yield.

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* Satisfactory analyses were obtained.

† Rotations were measured as 1% CHCl₃ solution at 25°.